

Effect of Combination of Glass Mat and Cloth on the Fatigue Properties of Fibrous Composite Materials

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ABSTRACT

This paper deals firstly with the pulsating tensile fatigue strength of chopped strand glass mat reinforced polyester and plane woven cloth reinforced polyester, with and without notches, secondly with the measured results of fatigue damage (whitening phenomena) and finally with the degradation of strength.

We describe the effect of the combination of glass mat and cloth on the fatigue properties of fibrous composite laminates, according to the experimental results on the above mentioned items. And we propose a simplified unit model because it has properties peculiar to the above mentioned laminates.

With the use of this model, we suggest an analytical approach to predicting the accumulation of damage in laminated composites by applying linear elastic fracture mechanics to the proposed simplified unit model for fibrous laminates.

MATERIALS AND TEST METHOD

Details of the tested laminated plates used in present work are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 The Constitution of Experimental Materials

	reinforcement	matrix	volume fraction of glass (%)	molding press	tensile strength (MPa)	elastic modulus (MPa)	remarks
Mat FRP	chopped strand glass mat 6ply	unsaturated polyester	22.7	hand-lay up	119.1	10690	—
Cloth FRP	plain fabrics glass cloth 20ply		34.8		229.4	16570	—
Cloth-Mat FRP	plain fabrics glass cloth 8ply chopped strand glass mat 4ply		25.9 (cloth 12.4) (mat 13.5)		149.9	13040	4C-4M-4C

Fig. 1 The Configuration of Test Specimen

These are fabricated by handlay-up method and cured at room temperature for 24 hours and aftercured for 4 hours at 80°C. The configurations of test specimens are illustrated in Fig. 1, (a) is for flat specimen, (b) is for notched specimen.

The static and pulsating tensile stress are applied on the test specimens mentioned above. The pulsating tensile stress with the frequency of 360, 600 cycles/minute are applied under the load controle of hydraulic servo system (name of fatigue testing machine: Tokyokoki-schenck Unipulse). During the fatigue test, we measured the whitening phenomena and the residual strength at several cycle ratios. the testing machine for the static test with cross head velocity of 5 mm/minute is Shimazu Autograph (IS 5000).

RESULTS OF TEST

Tensile strength and elastic modulus of experimental materials are shown in Table 1 and the S-N curves of specimens in this study are shown in Fig. 2. As shown in this figure, the fatigue life of cloth FRP is longer than that of mat FRP and the laminates with combined reinforcements is intermedially and strength degradations of notched specimens are recognized. According to the increase of stress cycle, the whitening range, thought as fatigue damage, appears at the neighborhood on the minimum cross section of specimen. Photo. 1 shows several examples of the state of whitening phenomena.

Fig. 2 The S-N Curves of Experimental Materials

Photo. 1 Examples of the Whitening Damage in Specimen

Fig. 3 Degradation of Residual Strength

SOME CONSIDERATION ON THE PROCESS OF FATIGUE

Various models have been proposed in order to describe the process of fatigue. However, these are not always the perfect models explaining the behavior of fatigue. As a proposal, we consider the cells peculiar to mat FRP and cloth FRP and mat FRP. The cell of cloth-mat FRP is composed of those of cloth FRP and mat FRP. The ratio of each cells is decided by the volume fraction of each cell. Fig. 4 shows the configuration of the cells of cloth FRP, mat FRP and cloth-mat FRP. The cell with respect to flat specimen is dealt with as one unit, since the applied stress of flat specimen is same everywhere in specimen. The cells with respect to notched specimen are dealt with as the parallel system at the cross section with notch, since the cross section with notched part has the highest applied stress level and the applied stress of each parts in this section is different on account of stress concentration.

Fig. 4 The Proposed Model of Fibrous Composite Laminates

FATIGUE FRACTURE MECHANISMS OF LAMINATES

As fiber reinforced composites contain preexisting flaws such as voids in original materials, the largest flaw may be assumed to play an important role in the tensile strength of composite. The relationship between crack growth rate and the range of stress intensity factors may be given by

$$\frac{dc_n}{dn} = \gamma (\Delta K)^\delta \tag{1}$$

Where c_n is the maximum crack length at n cycles and γ, δ are the material constants. ΔK may be equal to the stress intensity factor K in pulsating tensile stress. Under assumption of opening mode, K and fatigue fracture toughness K_{fc} are obtained as

$$K = \sigma \sqrt{\pi c_n} \beta \tag{2}$$

$$K_{fc} = \sigma_{Rn} \sqrt{\pi c_n} \beta \tag{3}$$

where β is constant for form.

Following relationship is given by using Equ. (1) (2) and (3)

$$\frac{dc_n}{dn} = \frac{dc_n}{d\sigma_{Rn}} \cdot \frac{d\sigma_{Rn}}{dn} = - 2/\pi \cdot K_{fc}^2 / \beta^2 \cdot 1/\sigma_{Rn}^3 \cdot \frac{d\sigma_{Rn}}{dn} \tag{4}$$

Substitution of Equ. (1),(2),(3) into (4) then results in

$$\frac{d\sigma_{Rn}}{dn} = -\pi \beta^2 \gamma K_{fc} (\delta - 2) / 2\sigma_{Rn}^{(\delta-3)} \cdot \sigma^\delta$$

By integrating from 0 to n, the following is derived

$$\sigma_{Rn} = (\sigma_{R1}^{(\delta-2)} / A n \sigma^\delta) \delta^{\frac{1}{\delta-2}} \quad (5)$$

where

$$A = \pi (\delta - 2) / 2 \cdot \gamma \beta^2 K_{fc}^{(\delta-2)} \quad (6)$$

A is function for applied stress, σ_{R1} is static tensile strength. With the assumption that laminate should fail under $\sigma_{Rn} \leq \sigma$, the number of cycles to failure N can be expressed by substituting $\sigma_{Rn} = \sigma$ into Eq. (5).

$$N = \sigma_{R1}^{(\delta-2)} - \sigma^{(\delta-2)} / A \sigma^\delta \quad (7)$$

Let's consider the compliance of laminate at n cycles λ_n . λ_n can be given by

$$\lambda_n = \lambda_0 + \Delta\lambda \quad (8)$$

, where λ_0 is the compliance of laminate without crack and $\Delta\lambda$ is the increment of compliance due to existence of crack. The elastic modulus of laminate at n cycles is shown by

$$E_n = 1/S\lambda_n \quad (9)$$

, where S and l are the cross sectional area and the length of the specimen, respectively $\Delta\lambda$ is obtained by summing up the increment of compliance by every cracks and is described as follows (1) (2)

$$\Delta\lambda = \xi K_{fc}^4 / AE_0 \sigma_{Rn}^4 \quad (10)$$

, where ξ is the coefficient which is decided by the number of cracks, the distribution of crack lengths and the mechanical properties of the specimen. E_0 is the elastic modulus of the specimen not existing any cracks, λ_0 is given by

$$\lambda_0 = 1/SE_0 \quad (11)$$

Substituting Eq. (8), (10) and (11) into Eq. (9), the following equation is obtained

$$E_n = E_0 / 1 + \frac{B}{\sigma_{Rn}^4} \quad (12)$$

, where $B = \frac{\xi K_{fc}^4}{E}$

Substituting Eq. (12) in the case of n=1 into Eq. (12) E_n is given by

$$E_n = E_1 \cdot 1 + \frac{B}{\sigma_{R1}^4} / 1 + \frac{B}{\sigma_{Rn}^4} \quad (13)$$

, where E_1 is the initial elastic modulus of the specimen.

Thus, it is proved that the elastic modulus at n cycles is represented as a function of residual strength σ_{Rn} .

The number of cycles to failure N in the case of the cells in parallel system is expressed as

$$N = \sum_{i=1}^k \Delta n_i$$

$$\Delta n_i = \sigma_{Ri}^{(\delta-2)} - \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} \alpha_j \sigma_j^\delta \Delta n_j - \sigma_i^{(\delta-2)} / \alpha_i \sigma_i^\delta$$

, where k is the number of cells and Δn_i is the number of cycles between the fracture of (i-1)-th cell and that of i-th cell.

COMPARISON ON THE ANALYTICAL AND THE EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

1. Calculation on the flat specimens

We can calculate the number of cycles to failure N using the Eq. (7), and A in the Eq. (7) is considered to be a function of applied stress level as follows.

$$A = a(\sigma - b) \quad (19)$$

Where a and b are constants for materials. The values of constants used in Eq. (7) and (19) are shown in Table 2.

Table 2 The Values of Constants

	δ	β	a	b	c
Mat FRP	12.75	160	1.8×10^{-5}	3.00	70
Cloth FRP	6.40	30000	1.63×10^{-6}	7.97	70

The curves in Fig. 2 are the analytical S-N curves using the above constants. The results of comparison on the experimental and analytical values show good coincidence as shown in Fig. 2.

2. Calculation on the notched specimens.

We divided the minimum cross section of specimen into 12 units as shown in Fig.5, in this figure ordinates are the ratio of partial strain (ϵ_p)

and mean strain (ϵ_m).

considering this strain distribution, the calculation of unit cell are proceeded. In this case, after the several trials of calculation, we arrived to the following procedure. This is, the strain concentration is released after the first unit cell's failure, and Young's modulus decreases according to the increase of strain as shown in the next relation.

$$\frac{E}{E_0} = 1 - C\epsilon$$

where C is constant of materials, and amounts of C in this case for each materials are shown in Table 2.

Fig. 5 Strain Distribution at the Minimum Cross Section

(a) Cloth FRP (b) Cloth-Mat FRP (c) Mat FRP

According to these procedure, the degradation of Young's modulus and the residual strength of each unit cell are estimated. Fig. 6 and Fig. 7 show the degradation of Young's modulus and residual strength.

Fig. 6 Degradation of Young's Modulus

(a) Cloth FRP (b) Cloth-Mat FRP (c) Mat FRP

Fig. 7 Degradation of Residual Strength

(a) Cloth FRP (b) Cloth-Mat FRP (c) Mat FRP

The solid line in Fig. 3 are obtained from the mean stress in Fig. 7 at each stress cycle ratio. And S-N curves in Fig. 2 are obtained from the basis of the analysis.

CONCLUSION

It is proved in the present work that the fatigue behaviors of glass fiber reinforced plastic laminates (Cloth FRP, Mat FRP and combined Cloth-Mat FRP) with and without notches can be well explained by calculating the fatigue damage of proposed symplified nait model by means of linear elastic fracture mechanics. Though the form of notch was U-notch, the method of analysis may be applied to the case with other type notches by the measurment of initial strain distribution, by setting the time of the release of strain concentration and the stress dependency of the residual modulus degradatation of unit cell.

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